

1 **Application of Physics-Informed Neural Networks to predict concentration profiles in**
2 **gradient liquid chromatography**

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12 **Abstract:**

13 Chromatography is one of the key methods in the analysis of mixture compositions, in the testing of
14 chemical purity, as well as in the production of highly pure compounds. For this reason, it finds an
15 important place in many industries. Currently, one of the most widely used techniques is gradient liquid
16 chromatography (GLC), which offers improved elution ability of the analytes. Experimental
17 determination of optimal separation parameters with GLC is tedious, hence various numerical methods
18 are used to optimize these processes. Recently, Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have
19 emerged as an alternative to classical numerical methods since they can also serve as a tool for solving
20 partial differential equations (PDEs). The main concept of the PINN, apart from the ability to detect
21 hidden and complex relationships between variables through machine learning, is to reach consistency
22 with the governing physical laws by using a loss function that takes PDEs into account, which allows
23 to obtain the results with better accuracy. In the paper, two PINN models are proposed, based on datasets
24 obtained from numerical solutions of the equilibrium dispersive (ED) chromatography column model.
25 After training and testing phases, the models are able to predict the concentration profiles under linear

26 and nonlinear GLC conditions with more than satisfactory accuracy. The first model (model A1) was
27 tested under linear GLC conditions, with variable inlet concentration or injection time, while the second
28 model (model A2) was validated both under linear and nonlinear GLC modes and with variable axial
29 dispersion and mass transport resistances.

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31 **Keywords:** Gradient Liquid Chromatography, Physics-Informed Neural Networks, Machine Learning,
32 Equilibrium-Dispersive Model

33

34 **Graphical abstract:**

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39 1. Introduction

40 Differential equations are essential for describing physical phenomena and are widely used in many
41 scientific fields from fluid mechanics, mass, and heat transfer [1] to quantum physics [2]. Numerical
42 methods, as a powerful simulation tool for solving these equations, play a crucial role in scientific
43 computing.

44 While numerical techniques such as finite differences method [3], finite volumes method [4], or finite
45 elements method [5] are useful in the investigation of complex problems, as well as in the designing
46 and optimizing of technological processes [6,7], they can be computationally demanding. Moreover,
47 producing highly accurate outcomes may require high-performance computing facilities.

48 An attractive alternative to numerical techniques that can provide quality output are deep learning
49 models capable of solving partial differential equations [8–11]. These models can reproduce the
50 behavior of physical phenomena using knowledge extracted from governing equations.

51 Early efforts to develop deep neural networks capable of solving differential equations (ODEs and
52 PDEs) were led by Lagaris et al. [9]. Later on, Raissi et al. [8] derived inspiration from their work and
53 designed Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), which can be applied to forward problems,
54 where the mathematical model is solved, and inverse problems, in which unknown parameters of
55 equations are estimated.

56 The PINNs have a sophisticated loss function that is physics-constrained to obey the governing
57 equations [8,10–12]. More specifically, its structure includes several strictly enforced terms that account
58 for the initial conditions, the boundary conditions, and the residual related to the PDEs. These terms
59 can be balanced by appropriate coefficients, known as weights, which are essential for obtaining precise
60 predictions and ensuring fast convergence [12].

61 In addition, once a PINN is trained, it allows for incredibly fast predictions for previously unseen data.
62 Furthermore, the PINNs can be updated for new cases through retraining and afterward successfully

63 applied in the presence of scarce and noisy data [13], which sets them apart from conventional deep
64 learning methods, requiring large datasets [14].

65 Recently, the PINN was applied for modeling separation in the chromatography column [15,16]. The
66 authors were able to predict the chromatography peaks profiles for Langmuir, anti-Langmuir, and a
67 combination of these isotherms with very good accuracy. In paper [17] PINNs were confirmed as a fast
68 and effective alternative and surrogate to classical numerical solutions enabling the control of
69 biopharmaceuticals production processes through both offline simulation of single-column
70 breakthrough curves and online optimization of load conditions for periodic counter-current
71 chromatography (PCC).

72 In this study, we present two PINN models for predicting the dynamics of a multicomponent gradient
73 liquid chromatography (GLC) process under various operating conditions without the necessity of
74 knowing adsorption isotherm forms and parameters (this concerns the algorithm for neural networks),
75 named A1 and A2.

76 In our work, we decided to deal with the problem of modeling gradient liquid chromatography (GLC),
77 which is a commonly used and productive technique with proven effectiveness in many fields [18].
78 With the growth of GLC applications, a demand for mathematical modeling has arisen in order to obtain
79 the possibility of predicting concentration profiles and further optimization of process conditions. The
80 problem of mathematical modeling of GLC is complex and requires the consideration of many variable
81 factors in solving partial differential equations describing the process, including parameters changed
82 intentionally (mobile phase composition and flowrate, injection volume) and spontaneously (pressure,
83 temperature, physicochemical parameters of mobile and stationary phase) during the process.

84 The problem of GLC modeling appears in several works using linear and nonlinear retention models of
85 modifier concentration and various sophisticated analytical and numerical techniques including i.a. the
86 finite difference method with the Craig scheme [19], Laplace transform approach for analytical solution
87 of the LC transport model [20], flux-limiting finite volume numerical method for the LC lumped kinetic
88 model [21], and discontinuous Galerkin finite element method for equilibrium dispersive model [22].

89 However, due to the computationally demanding nature of currently available methods and the
90 emergence of new solutions based on machine learning, this problem requires further development. The
91 decision to pursue the subject of GLC chromatography modeling using PINN is influenced by two
92 motives. The first is to provide solutions enabling prediction of solute concentration profiles under
93 gradient chromatography conditions, taking into account also nonlinear and step-type variants. The
94 second is to verify the capabilities of the PINN approach in solving practical problems involving
95 complex GLC processes.

96 In the initial stage of our research, Model A1 was designed to simulate elution curves with a linear
97 gradient mode in relation to changes in input process parameters such as inlet concentrations or injection
98 times for both one-component systems, containing an analyte and a modifier (called in the following
99 binary model) and two-component systems with two various analytes and a modifier (called in the
100 following ternary model). Due to the limitations of this model which prevented the implementation of
101 planned scenarios, it was subsequently expanded and evolved into Model A2 to accommodate
102 additional cases, for instance where two variables, such as inlet concentration and time gradient (τ_g)
103 are modified simultaneously. By presenting two models, we intend to present the stages of the research
104 process, i.e. the evolution of our approach as the subject matter was explored. However, Model A1 is
105 recommended for solving simpler linear gradient chromatography cases since the training times
106 required to gain the desired performance are approximately 30% shorter comparing to the more versatile
107 Model A2.

108 When the linear gradient does not allow for the complete separation of compounds then a sequential
109 linear gradient or a nonlinear gradient of any shape can increase separation and simultaneously decrease
110 the time of the process. The proposed improved Model A2–enables modeling the dynamics of the
111 chromatography process in gradient elution mode with linear or nonlinear profile.

112 Both aforementioned models were trained on datasets derived from numerical experiments and tested
113 on previously unseen input data as well. The main objective of our study was to demonstrate that the
114 PINNs can effectively predict concentration profiles in GLC over a wide range of parameter variations

115 while allowing the model to uncover the thermodynamic equilibrium of the adsorption-desorption
116 process during training, described by a complex isotherm. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first
117 report on the application of the PINNs in GLC.

118

119 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: **Section 2** provides an insight into the
120 chromatographic column model utilized to perform *in silico* modeling of the analyte separation process
121 by gradient liquid chromatography. **Section 3** introduces issues related to applied neural network
122 architectures, proposed loss functions, hyperparameters, and dimensionality reduction of the ED model.
123 **Section 4** describes data generation and shows comparisons of the PINNs' performance with exact
124 solutions for various specific cases. **Section 5** concludes our main findings and provides suggestions
125 for further research.

126 2. Governing Partial Differential Equations

127 The objective of the physics-informed neural networks is to capture the behavior of complex process
128 dynamics by solving partial differential equations. Herein, we applied the frequently used equilibrium-
129 dispersive (ED) model to incorporate knowledge pertaining to chromatographic separation dynamics
130 into the learning process. Overall, the ED model describes the dynamics of component separation
131 alongside the chromatographic column under the assumption of no mass transfer resistance between the
132 adsorbent particles and the mobile phase as well as inside pores of the particles [23,24].

133 In our research the following governing equation was adopted, presented by Kaczmarek et al. [24]:

$$134 \quad \varepsilon_t \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + (1 - \varepsilon_t) \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial z} = \varepsilon_e D_L \frac{\partial^2 c_i}{\partial z^2} \quad i = 1, \dots, N_c \quad (1)$$

135 In the above equation, ε_t , ε_e [-] is total column porosity and bulk porosity, respectively, c [g/dm³] and
136 q [g/dm³] is concentration in mobile and stationary state, respectively, N_c is the number of components,
137 D_L [m²/s] denotes the dispersion coefficient, u [m/s] is mobile phase flow rate, t is time in [s] and z [m]
138 is coordinate along the column axis. A detailed Glossary is attached to Supplementary materials.

139 Equation (1) has to be coupled with the initial and the boundary conditions:

140 The initial conditions (at $t = 0$) are:

141 for $0 < z < L$; $c_i(0, z) = c_i^o$; $q_i(0, z) = q_i^o$ (2)

142 The boundary conditions at the column inlet are:

143 for $t > 0$; $z = 0$; $u_f c'_{f,i} = u(0)c_i(t, 0) - \varepsilon_e D_L \frac{\partial c_i(t,z)}{\partial z}$ (3a)

144 for Danckwerts conditions

145 or $c_i(t, 0) = c'_{f,i}$ (3b)

146 for Dirichlet conditions

147 with $c'_{f,i} = c_{f,i}$ for $t \in [0, t_p]$ and with $c'_{f,i} = 0$ for $t > t_p$. (4)

148 The boundary conditions at the column outlet are:

149 for $t > 0$; $z = L$ $\frac{\partial c_i(t,z)}{\partial z} = 0$ (5)

150 where t_p [s] is injection time.

151 Equation (1) is solved with the adsorption model as shown in Eq. (6).

152 $q_i = f(q_s, K_1, \dots, K_{Nc}, c_1, \dots, c_{Nc})$ (6)

153 where q_s denotes saturation capacity, and K_1, \dots, K_{Nc} are the equilibrium constants.

154 The following we assumed: $c_i^o = 0$; $u(0) = u_f$ and $c_{f,i}$ is given in the text.

155 In the proposed PINN models, information about the adsorption model described by Eq. 6 is not

156 provided, thus it is treated as unknown. For this reason, q_i is estimated during the training process based

157 on the numerical solution of the model Eq. 1 – Eq. 6.

158 More general information about the process is obtained when analysis is performed in a dimensionless

159 version of the ED model. It should be also noticed that different physical dimensions of inputs during

160 the neural network training can lead to low prediction accuracy and slow convergence. To mitigate this

161 issue, the applied quantities have been normalized as follows:

162 $x = \frac{z}{L} \quad \tau = \frac{t}{t_0} \quad y = \frac{c}{c_r} \quad Q = \frac{q}{c_r} \quad Q_s = \frac{q_s}{c_r} \quad Pe = \frac{uL}{D_L \varepsilon_e}$ (7)

163 where

164 $t_0 = \frac{L \cdot \varepsilon_e}{u}$ and q_s is saturation capacity (8)

165 and c_r was assumed to be equal to 1 [g/dm³].

166 Additionally, the case-specific parameters such as Peclet number, parameters characterizing the
 167 gradient of modifier t_g , and some others parameters have been normalized to be within the range of
 168 [0.25, 1]. These parameters, denoted by ξ , have been calculated according to the map:

169 $f(\xi; \xi_{\min}; \xi_{\max}) := 0.75 \left(\frac{\xi - \xi_{\min}}{\xi_{\max} - \xi_{\min}} \right) + 0.25$ (9)

170 where ξ_{\min} is the lower limit and ξ_{\max} is the upper limit of the given parameter ξ .

171 By substituting the individual variables from Eq. (7) into Eqs. (1 – 6), the following dimensionless form
 172 of the ED model has been obtained:

173 $\frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \tau} + \frac{(1-\varepsilon_t)}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial x} = \frac{\varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{1}{Pe} \frac{\partial^2 y_i}{\partial x^2}$ (10)

174 where $i = 1, \dots, Nc$, Nc denotes modifier and $i = 1, \dots, Nc - 1$ are indexes of analytes.

175 Assuming that the modifier does not adsorb, so $Q_{Nc} = 0$.

176 Moreover, the concentration of the modifier is denoted with a frequently used literature symbol "φ"
 177 which also stands for a volume fraction of the modifier.

178 The dimensionless initial and boundary conditions for analytes are:

179 The initial conditions (at $\tau = 0$):

180 for $0 < x < L$; $y_i(0, x) = y_i^0$ (11)

181 The boundary conditions at the column inlet are:

182 for $\tau > 0$; $x = 0$; $y'_{f,i} = y_i(\tau, 0) - \frac{1}{Pe} \frac{\partial y_i(\tau, x)}{\partial x}$ (12a)

183 for Danckwerts conditions, or

$$184 \quad y_i(\tau, 0) = y'_{f,i} \quad (12b)$$

185 for Dirichlet conditions

$$186 \quad \text{where} \quad y'_{f,i} = \begin{cases} y_{f,i} & \text{for } \tau \in [0, \tau_p] \\ 0 & \text{for } \tau > \tau_p \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$187 \quad \text{for } \tau > 0; x = 1 \quad \frac{\partial y_i(\tau, x)}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (14)$$

188 Assuming the linear gradient of the modifier its dimensionless concentration $y_{f,NC}$ is as follows:

$$189 \quad y_{f,NC} = \varphi(\tau, 0) = \begin{cases} \varphi_0, & 0 \leq \tau < \tau_b \\ \varphi_0 + \frac{\Delta\varphi}{\tau_g}(\tau - \tau_b), & \tau_b \leq \tau < \tau_b + \tau_g \\ \varphi_0 + \Delta\varphi, & \tau_b + \tau_g \leq \tau \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

190 where φ_0 is the fraction of organic modifier in the mobile phase at the beginning of the gradient, τ_b is
191 the time when the gradient reaches the column inlet, $\Delta\varphi$ is the change in modifier fraction between the
192 beginning and the end of the gradient and τ_g is the duration of the gradient. In the following, we assumed
193 that, τ_b is equal to τ_p .

194 Assuming the linear solvent strength (LSS) theory [25] the test of the PINN was done for gradient
195 chromatography.

196 The adsorption isotherm dependence on the organic modifier in analytical conditions becomes:

$$197 \quad Q_i(y, \varphi) = Q_s K_i e^{-S_i \varphi} y_i \quad (16)$$

198 where: Q_s is the saturation capacity, K_i is the equilibrium constant in the pure mobile phase, while S is
199 a parameter describing the organic modifier dependence of the adsorption process.

200 3. The Background of the Artificial Neural Networks

201 The Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are universal function approximators that use the
202 backpropagation algorithm to adjust their internal parameters. The ANNs are composed of neurons
203 organized into various layers, i.e. an input layer (leftmost), hidden layers, and an output layer

204 (rightmost) – see Fig. 1. Neurons in adjacent layers are interconnected with the influence of each
 205 connection determined by specific weights. Each layer serves a distinct role; hence the input layer
 206 receives raw data, the hidden layers process the input data and the output layer provides the result of
 207 the neural network’s computation, which is subsequently used by the loss function to evaluate the
 208 discrepancy between the prediction and the target values [26].

209 In the pipeline of neural networks, data flows forward, i.e. from the left to the right side. Therefore,
 210 considering a fully connected neural network with a total $l+2$ layers, where l represents the number of
 211 hidden layers, and $l-1$ refers to the input layer. The output of the hidden layers, O^l , can be computed
 212 as:

$$213 \quad O^l = \sigma^l(O^{l-1}W^l + b^l) \quad (17)$$

214 where σ^l is the nonlinear activation function, O^{l-1} is the output from the preceding layer,
 215 $W^l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{l-1} \times n_l}$ is the weight matrix for layer, l , n_{l-1} is the number of the neurons in the previous layer,
 216 n_l is the number of neurons in the current layer, $b^l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ is the bias vector in the layer, l .

217 The Physics-Informed Neural Networks are advanced machine learning models based on a multilayer
 218 feed-forward neural network architecture. The essence of a PINN is to find a function that maps inputs
 219 to outputs, which can be accomplished by utilizing data collected from experiments, such as numerical
 220 ones, and by integrating knowledge derived from the provided physical laws. A detailed explanation of
 221 the PINN loss will be presented in **Section 3.2**.

222 In this study, two PINN models have been presented (Fig. 1), called A1 and A2, which were designed
 223 to predict concentration profiles in GLC under various operating conditions.

224

225 **Fig. 1.** Schematic illustration of the proposed PINN models. (A) shows the architecture of Model A1,
 226 which takes three inputs x , τ , ω , and predicts concentration profiles for the elution mode with linear
 227 gradient. (B) shows Model A2, which accepts four inputs x , τ , ω , ξ , and is utilized for modeling
 228 concentration profiles in linear and nonlinear gradient modes. The symbol θ corresponds to a matrix of
 229 trainable parameters, i.e. weights and biases, while θ^* represents their state upon completion of training.
 230 On the right side of the schemes for models A1 and A2, the construction of the total loss function is
 231 illustrated, which includes the initial conditions, the boundary conditions, and the PDE residual. Note
 232 that the randomly generated points (τ, x) were used here to satisfy the governing equations inside the
 233 domain. To be consistent with the literature the randomly generated (τ, x) points are called collocation
 234 points or spatiotemporal points.

235

236 **3.1. PINN Models**

237 In order to model the separation of analytes via elution gradient mode, a fully connected deep neural
238 network architecture was applied. Solving partial differential equations (PDEs) with the PINNs is
239 performed through the automatic differentiation (AD) procedure [27].

240 For both models, soft boundary enforcement [8,28,29] was applied, where penalty terms are encoded
241 into the loss function to enforce the Dirichlet boundary conditions or the Danckwerts boundary
242 conditions. As inputs, measurements from numerical experiments and randomly selected collocation
243 points were utilized to satisfy the PDE residuals inside the domain.

244 To investigate the capability of the PINN models for predicting elution curves in GLC two models were
245 designed for different scenarios.

246 **Scenario 1:** We assumed that in linear gradient elution, the inlet concentration or the injection time is
247 varied while keeping other parameters constant.

248 **Scenario 2:** We assumed variations in the time of the gradient, Peclet number, parameter S describing
249 the organic modifier dependence of analyte retention (see Eq. (16)), and other parameters, where
250 modifier concentration changes linearly or non-linearly.

251 In the early stages of research, the model called A1 was implemented, which accepts three input
252 parameters, to realize Scenario 1. Subsequently, an expanded version, named A2, was designed which
253 involves four inputs and differs in the penalty terms of the loss function. This model enabled us to
254 accomplish the Scenario 2. In the aforementioned models, information about the equilibrium between
255 the mobile and the stationary phases is estimated during training. Further details concerning the models
256 architecture can be found in **Section 3.1.1** and **Section 3.1.2**.

257 **3.1.1. Model A1**

258 As shown in Fig. 1, Model A1 takes spatiotemporal points x , τ , as well as inlet concentration and
259 injection time as input variables, denoted as ω . The dimensionless concentration in the mobile phase \hat{y}
260 and in the stationary phase \hat{Q} constitute the outputs. This architecture was designed to predict elution

261 curves with respect to changes in inlet concentration and injection time in linear gradient mode and was
 262 tested in linear gradient mode.

263 **3.1.2. Model A2**

264 Afterward, our intent was to solve more challenging cases. To tackle these, Model 2 was developed and
 265 augmented by an additional input parameter ξ , which allows to handle a broader range of scenarios
 266 where input parameters, such as the time gradient (τ_g), the Peclet number or others can be varied. The
 267 outputs are dimensionless concentrations in the mobile phase \hat{y} and in the stationary phase \hat{Q} . The model
 268 has been adapted for both linear and nonlinear gradients.

269 **3.2. Loss function**

270 In the PINNs, similarly to other neural networks, the optimal trainable parameters are sought to
 271 minimize the overall loss function. Developing an appropriate loss function is crucial for fast
 272 convergence and quality of the resulting predictions. The total loss \mathcal{L} is calculated as the sum of two
 273 loss terms from the PDE residual term $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}$, which incorporates the physical laws and the data loss \mathcal{L}_{Data} ,
 274 which measures the discrepancy between the model predictions and labeled data. In general, it can be
 275 expressed as:

$$276 \quad \mathcal{L}(\theta; N_{\mathcal{R}}; N_{Data}) = \lambda_{\mathcal{R}} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\theta; N_{\mathcal{R}}) + \mathcal{L}_{Data}(\theta; N_{Data}) \quad (18)$$

277 where $\theta = [W, b]$ corresponds to trainable parameters; $N_{\mathcal{R}}$ indicates collocation points; N_{Data} denotes
 278 experimentally derived data points, $\lambda_{\mathcal{R}}$ is a weight term associated with the residual part of the loss
 279 function. Herein, each constituent of the total loss is expressed through the Mean Squared Error (MSE).

280 It is important to highlight that, the data loss term determines the match between the model solution and
 281 correct answer on the initial (*I.C.*) and the boundary (*B.C.*) points, while the model is penalized for
 282 mass balance violations of the governing equation. Therefore \mathcal{L}_{Data} can be written as:

$$283 \quad \mathcal{L}_{Data}(\theta; N_{Data}) = \mathcal{L}_{I.C.}(\theta; N_{I.C.}) + \mathcal{L}_{B.C.}(\theta; N_{B.C.}) \quad (19)$$

284 where $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.}$ is related to the boundary loss at $x = 0$ ($\mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}$) and at $x = 1$ ($\mathcal{L}_{B.C.2}$), and is given by:

$$285 \quad \mathcal{L}_{B.C.}(\theta; N_{B.C.1}; N_{B.C.2}) = \mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}(\theta; N_{B.C.1}) + \lambda_{B.C.2} \mathcal{L}_{B.C.2}(\theta; N_{B.C.2}) \quad (20)$$

286 where $\lambda_{B.C.2}$ is the weight term of the second boundary loss term.

287 Thus, the overall loss function to be minimized for both models can be written as:

$$288 \quad \mathcal{L}(\theta; N_{\mathcal{R}}; N_{I.C.}; N_{B.C.}) = \lambda_{\mathcal{R}} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\theta; N_{\mathcal{R}}) + \mathcal{L}_{I.C.}(\theta; N_{I.C.}) + \mathcal{L}_{B.C.}(\theta; N_{B.C.}) \quad (21)$$

289 3.2.1 Loss function formula for Model A1

290 As mentioned above, the loss function consists of two terms: $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}$ and \mathcal{L}_{Data} . The first term enforces the
 291 governing equations, while the second ensures the fulfillment of initial and boundary conditions.

292 $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}$ is defined as:

$$293 \quad \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\theta; N_{\mathcal{R}}) = \frac{1}{N_{\mathcal{R}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\mathcal{R}}} \left| \frac{\partial \hat{y}_i}{\partial \tau} + \frac{(1-\varepsilon_t) \partial \hat{Q}_i}{\varepsilon_t \partial \tau} + \frac{\varepsilon_e \partial \hat{y}_i}{\varepsilon_t \partial x} - \frac{\varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_t P e} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{y}_i}{\partial x^2} \right|^2 \quad (22)$$

294 where $N_{\mathcal{R}}$ represents the number of points in experiment time 3. Multiplication by 3 follows from using
 295 3 different values of training parameters, see e.g. Fig. S1, where $y_1 = 16$; $y_2 = 11$; $y_3 = 7.5$. The same
 296 is true for Eqs. 23-31.

297 The individual derivatives, i.e. $\frac{\partial y}{\partial \tau}$, $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \tau}$, $\frac{\partial y}{\partial x}$, $\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2}$, are computed using automatic differentiation, a method
 298 based on the chain rule [27].

299 The loss for the initial conditions is as follows:

$$300 \quad \mathcal{L}_{I.C.}(\theta; N_{I.C.}) = \frac{1}{N_{I.C.}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{I.C.}} |\hat{y}(x_{i,I.C.}, 0, \omega, \theta) - 0|^2 + \frac{1}{N_{I.C.}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{I.C.}} |\hat{Q}(x_{i,I.C.}, 0, \omega, \theta) - 0|^2 \quad (23)$$

301 Since the chromatographic column is initially not filled with an analyte and no substance is adsorbed
 302 onto the stationary phase, the value 0 in the above equations serves as the reference value.

303 The remaining terms of the loss function enforce the boundary conditions. For $x = 0$ and the Dirichlet
 304 conditions, the loss is expressed as:

$$305 \quad \mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}(\theta; N_{B.C.1}) = \frac{1}{N_{B.C.1}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{B.C.1}} |\hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \omega, \theta) - y(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \omega, \theta)|^2 \quad (24)$$

306 and for the Danckwerts conditions is

307 $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}(\theta; N_{B.C.1}) = \frac{1}{N_{B.C.1}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{B.C.1}} \left| \hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \omega, \theta) - \frac{1}{Pe} \frac{\partial \hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \omega, \theta)}{\partial x} - \right.$

308 $\left. y(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \omega, \theta) \right|^2$ (25)

309 For $x = 1$ the loss is formulated as follows:

310 $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.2}(\theta; N_{B.C.2}) = \frac{1}{N_{B.C.2}} \sum_i^{N_{B.C.2}} \left| \hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.2}, \tau_{i,B.C.2}, \omega, \theta) - y(x_{i,B.C.2}, \tau_{i,B.C.2}, \omega, \theta) \right|^2$ (26)

311 The terms $N_{\mathcal{R}}$, $N_{I.C.}$, $N_{B.C.1}$, $N_{B.C.2}$ refer to collocation points inside the domain that constrain the model
 312 to follow the partial differential equation, the points associated with the initial conditions, and the
 313 boundary points at the two ends of the domain, respectively.

314 3.2.2 Loss function formula for Model A2

315 The second model is built upon the previous one, introducing an extended formulation for the loss
 316 function.

317 The governing equation loss $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}$ is expressed as:

318 $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\theta; N_{\mathcal{R}}) = \frac{1}{N_{\mathcal{R}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\mathcal{R}}} \left| \frac{\partial \hat{y}_i}{\partial \tau} + \frac{(1-\varepsilon_t)}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial \hat{Q}_i}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial \hat{y}_i}{\partial x} - \frac{\varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{1}{Pe} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{y}_i}{\partial x^2} \right|^2$ (27)

319 The loss for the initial conditions $\mathcal{L}_{I.C.}$ is given by:

320 $\mathcal{L}_{I.C.}(\theta; N_{I.C.}) = \frac{1}{N_{I.C.}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{I.C.}} \left| \hat{y}(x_i, 0, \xi, \omega, \theta) - 0 \right|^2 + \frac{1}{N_{I.C.}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{I.C.}} \left| \hat{Q}(x_i, 0, \xi, \omega, \theta) - 0 \right|^2$ (28)

321 The boundary conditions are enforced through two separate terms. For the boundary at $x = 0$, the loss
 322 $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}$ is defined as:

323 $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}(\theta; N_{B.C.1}) = \frac{1}{N_{B.C.1}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{B.C.1}} \left| \hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \xi, \omega, \theta) - y(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \xi, \omega, \theta) \right|^2$ (29)

324 for the Dirichlet conditions,

325 $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.1}(\theta; N_{B.C.1}) = \frac{1}{N_{B.C.1}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{B.C.1}} \left| \hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \xi, \omega, \theta) - \frac{1}{Pe} \frac{\partial \hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \xi, \omega, \theta)}{\partial x} - \right.$

326 $\left. y(x_{i,B.C.1}, \tau_{i,B.C.1}, \xi, \omega, \theta) \right|^2$ (30)

327 and the Danckwerts conditions.

328 For the boundary at $x = 1$ the loss $\mathcal{L}_{B.C.2}$ is described as:

$$329 \quad \mathcal{L}_{B.C.2}(\theta; N_{B.C.2}) = \frac{1}{N_{B.C.2}} \sum_i^{N_{B.C.2}} |\hat{y}(x_{i,B.C.2}, \tau_{i,B.C.2}, \xi, \omega, \theta) - y(x_{i,B.C.2}, \tau_{i,B.C.2}, \xi, \omega, \theta)|^2 \quad (31)$$

330 where ξ stands for the Peclet number, τ_g , α , $\Delta\varphi$ or S – see Eq (16)

331 **3.3. Hyperparameters**

332 It is well known that the selection of appropriate hyperparameters influences the success of the neural
333 network learning process. Hyperparameters that affect this process include the size of the network, i.e.
334 the number of neurons, n , layers, l , the optimizer type, the learning rate, and the type of activation
335 function, σ^l , [30,31]. In our experiments, the number of hidden layers l was set to 8 with 10 neurons
336 per layer. The employed differentiable activation function was the hyperbolic tangent (tanh), which is
337 a common choice in many PINN approaches [32–36]. In our study the L-BFGS optimizer [37], a quasi-
338 Newton method with default learning rate was applied, as well as history size equal to 110, and strong
339 Wolfe line search.

340 **3.4. Learning Procedure**

341 Training the PINN is performed by minimizing the total loss function shown in Eq. (18 or 21). This
342 process leads to finding the optimal trainable parameters θ . However, these parameters must be first
343 initialized in order to begin training. The choice of the appropriate initialization technique has a
344 significant impact on the convergence rate [38]. Different ways of initializing weights can be found in
345 literature, such as random initialization, Kaiming initialization [39] or Glorot initialization (also
346 commonly referred to as Xavier initialization) [38].

347 Herein, the weights of both models were initialized via Glorot initialization, while the biases were
348 initialized with zeros, which is a common strategy in NN. The L-BFGS optimizer was used to minimize
349 the total loss function. After each iteration, the back-propagation algorithm calculates the gradients of
350 the loss function with respect to the internal NN parameters, using the chain rule. Then, the optimizer
351 utilizes these gradients to update the parameters and minimize the loss function. In addition, partial
352 derivatives of an output with respect to an input that is present in the PDE residuals are computed by
353 automatic differentiation (AD). The AD procedure is available in the TensorFlow [40] package via

354 *tf.gradients()* as well as in the PyTorch library through *torch.autograd.grad()* [41]. The training
355 procedure is repeated until satisfactory convergence is achieved, i.e. the parameters are found, yielding
356 a model that produces the smallest possible error.

357 **3.5 Data normalization and dimensionless quantities**

358 Different physical dimensions of inputs during the neural network training can lead to low prediction
359 accuracy and slow convergence. To mitigate this issue, the quantities used in modelling have been
360 normalized as defined in **Section 2**.

361 The training of the NN requires a numerical solution of the ED model – in our case in its dimensionless
362 form Eqs. (7 – 16). The model was solved with the Orthogonal Collocation on Finite Element (OCFE)
363 method [23,42], common in the modeling of chemical engineering processes, especially chemical
364 reactors. From the mathematical point of view, the ED model is a set of nonlinear parabolic partial
365 differential equations. An effective technique for solving PDEs is the method of lines, in which the
366 spatial derivatives are approximated with the suitable numerical procedure – in our case the OCFE. In
367 the OCFE method, column length (space coordinate – z) is divided into NS subdomains, commonly
368 referred to as finite elements. Typically, in each subdomain, NICP internal collocation points are chosen
369 as the roots of the NICP-th order Legendre polynomial. However, in this work, we have chosen the
370 equidistant position of collocation points inside the subdomain. This maneuver remarkably facilitates
371 interconnection between the numerical method and the Neural Network. It slightly can increase of time
372 of calculation but does not influence the accuracy of computation. The unknown function is represented
373 within each element by an interpolating polynomial which is continuous and has continuous derivatives.
374 The details of approximate spatial derivatives by algebraic equations using the OCFE method can be
375 found in our previous work [43] in which equations for fixed and moving finite elements are presented.
376 In this work, we applied a code for the fixed finite elements. The NICP was assumed to be equal to 3
377 and NS were selected so that their further increase did not improve the obtained solution.

378 The other recommended method for numerical solving of PDEs is a weighted essentially non-oscillatory
379 (WENO) scheme [44,45]. The WENO algorithm is used to approximate the convection term in the PDE.
380 The non-oscillatory character of this scheme enables to use a coarser net of nodal points which can

381 reduce the computation time. The second derivative term of the PDE is calculated with a second-order
382 centered difference approximation. The number of nodal points, as in the case of the OCFE method,
383 was selected so that their further increase did not improve the obtained solution.

384 In this work, the WENO method and the Dirichlet boundary conditions were used when $Pe \geq 200$, if
385 it was not stated otherwise. For the cases when $Pe < 200$ the Danckwerts boundary conditions and the
386 OCFE were applied because, as it was proved in [46], the Dirichlet boundary conditions are applicable
387 only when $Pe/2$ is greater than about 100.

388 A set of ODEs is obtained after the discretization of spatial derivatives. It should be noted that
389 chromatography column models belong to so-called stiff models, so the obtained set also belongs to
390 them. The obtained set of ODEs was solved with the CVODE solver which includes the BDF method
391 for stiff equations [47]. The relative error of computation was set to 10^{-6} and the absolute error to 10^{-8} .
392 The CVODE solver is regarded as one of the best available ODE solvers [48]. The accuracy and
393 correctness of the simulation compared with other robust numerical methods are discussed in [49].

394

395 **4. Results and discussion**

396 **4.1. PINN Implementation and Predictive Performance**

397 In this study, the PINN models were implemented using the PyTorch library. The neural networks were
398 trained using a single NVIDIA A100 GPU with 40 GB of memory. For each specific case, the model
399 was trained on three concentration profiles, individually for each analyte with computational times
400 ranging from 5 to 11 minutes, depending on the type of model and the scenario considered.

401 To evaluate the discrepancy between the exact solution and the predicted solution the relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
402 is evaluated as follows:

$$403 \quad \mathcal{L}_2 = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i|^2}} \quad (32)$$

404 where \hat{y}_i is the PINN solution, y_i is the ED model solution, and n is the number of spatiotemporal
405 points.

406 Datasets for PINN training are presented in Figures, and included in Supplementary material.docx.

407 **4.2. Weight Terms and Collocation Points**

408 An essential aspect is the selection of appropriate weight terms in the loss function. However, this is
409 not an easy task and is closely related to the specific case under consideration. There are no strict rules
410 for determining these values, therefore the ratio of the individual λ is established experimentally. In the
411 course of our research, the best results for both models were achieved with a ratio, $\lambda_{\mathcal{R}}: \lambda_{B,C,2}$ set to
412 1:100.

413 In addition, to acquire solutions for the PDEs (Eq. 22 and Eq. 27), 5000 randomly sampled
414 spatiotemporal points (x,τ) were utilized. These collocation points within the domain were generated
415 using the Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) [50] strategy.

416 **4.3. Data generation**

417 Synthetic data for model training were generated by solving the equilibrium-dispersive column model.
418 For approximate solutions of the PDEs, the OCFE or the WENO method was used as stated above.
419 A single input chromatogram comprised an injection pulse and elution profile, where each curve
420 consists of 2200 points. Table 1 lists the parameters for the chromatographic column models.

421

422 **Table 1** The scope of parameter values used for solving the ED model to obtain high-fidelity synthetic
423 data.

424

Parameter	Unit	Range of values
Q_s	[-]	8
K_1	[-]	8
K_2	[-]	10

u	[-]	1
ε_t	[-]	0.7
ε_e	[-]	0.4
Pe_1	[-]	[5;2000]
Pe_2	[-]	[5;2000]
Pe_3	[-]	[5;10000]
τ_p	[-]	[0.025;0.25]
y_1^0	[-]	[1;16]
y_2^0	[-]	[1;16]
φ_0	[v/v]	0
τ_g	[-]	[2;70]
$\Delta\varphi$	[v/v]	[0.2;0.6]
α	[-]	[0.7;1]
S_1	[-]	[7;13]
S_2	[-]	[7;15]

425

426

427 **4.4. Model A1: use cases**

428 The capabilities of this PINN model, which was designed in the first phase of the research, as previously
429 mentioned, were demonstrated on cases where concentration profiles are predicted in situations where
430 the inlet concentration or injection time are varied. Assuming that the linear adsorption model is
431 described by Eq. (16), by analogy to isocratic isotherm models the GLC models can be created. For one
432 analyte and a modifier, the Langmuir isotherm model reads:

$$433 \quad Q(y, \varphi) = \frac{Q_s K_1 e^{-S_1 \varphi} y}{1 + K_1 e^{-S_1 \varphi} y} \quad (33)$$

434 For two analytes and a modifier, the competitive Langmuir isotherm model reads:

$$435 \quad Q_i(y_1, y_2, \varphi) = \frac{Q_{s,i}K_i e^{-S_i\varphi} y_i}{1 + K_1 e^{-S_1\varphi} y_1 + K_2 e^{-S_2\varphi} y_2} \quad i = 1,2 \quad (34)$$

436 Isotherms Eq. (33) and Eq. (34) were the basic adsorption models for which the proposed PINN method
437 was validated.

438 In this section, the simplest process of gradient chromatography separation using the linear gradient of
439 the modifier was analyzed. Modifiers can facilitate the separation process, decrease the time of analyses,
440 and increase the productivity of column chromatography.

441 The analyte concentration profile depends on the fraction of a modifier in the mobile phase. φ_0 , at the
442 beginning of the gradient, the time when the gradient reaches the column inlet, τ_b , the change in
443 modifier fraction between the beginning and the end of the gradient $\Delta\varphi$, and the duration of the gradient
444 τ_g .

445 The simplest case is a linear gradient – the concentration of a modifier is changed linearly in time at the
446 column inlet and linearly along the column and can be defined with Eq. (15).

447 At the very beginning, the PINN framework was trained on the dataset displayed in Fig. S1, where
448 individual numerical experiments were performed with immutable injection times, τ_p , gradient times
449 τ_g and Peclet numbers presented in Table 2, whereas y_0 was modified as follows: 7.5; 11; and 16
450 (Table 2 **B1^{A1}**). Subsequently, modeling was carried out on a ternary system (**T1^{A1}**) involving the elution
451 of two analytes and modifiers with y_1 and y_2 being equal to 1.85, 2.50, and 3.90 (Fig. S2).

452 In the second stage of the Model A1 tests, its prediction capability in conditions of diverse injection
453 times was examined. In the first attempt, **B2^{A1}** case was explored, in which the neural network was
454 trained on the dataset presented in Fig. S3 with τ_p , corresponding to 25%, 50%, and 100% of the
455 maximum value of 0.23. Likewise, for the system involving the separation of two analytes (**T2^{A1}**),
456 various injection times were applied and the gathered data for training purposes are shown in Fig. S4.

457

458 **Table 2** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with different inlet
 459 concentrations (**B1^{A1}**, **T1^{A1}**) and injection times (**B2^{A1}**, **T2^{A1}**).

Experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe
	7.5	0.05	70	1000
B1^{A1}	11	0.05	70	1000
	16	0.05	70	1000
	1.85	0.05	40	1000
T1^{A1}	2.50	0.05	40	1000
	3.90	0.05	40	1000
	1	0.02	50	1000
B2^{A1}	1	0.09	50	1000
	1	0.23	50	1000
	2	0.10	30	1000
T2^{A1}	2	0.15	30	1000
	2	0.25	30	1000

460

461

462 **Note for all of the Tables:**

463 • **B** denotes binary system,

464 • **T** denotes ternary system,

465 • ^{A1} superscript indicates the type of model applied to the case,

466 If it was not stated otherwise:

467 • the inlet concentration y_0 is the same for y_1 and y_2 compound,

468 • if no value is given to the parameters S_1 and S_2 in the Tables, this means that $S_1 = 10$ and $S_2 = 15$

469 are used.

470

471 **4.4.1. Performance of predicting elution curves under diverse inlet concentrations or**
 472 **injection times**

473 In Fig. 2 a comparison between the PINN solutions and the numerical results is presented. The data for
 474 calculation are given in Table 3. As observed, the predictive capability for varying inlet concentrations
 475 in the binary system (Fig. 2A) shows small deviations from the exact solution. The same observation
 476 applies to the ternary system, where the concentration profiles of analytes 1 and 2 almost perfectly
 477 match the numerical results. The dataset for this case is provided in Fig. S2. Subsequently, the results
 478 shown in Fig. 2C-D correspond to scenarios where the injection time was varied. For both the binary
 479 and the ternary systems, a slight discrepancy between the PINN predictions and the numerical results
 480 can be observed.

481 Because optical comparison of peak shapes can be unreliable, the relative \mathcal{L}_2 error – see Table 3 was
 482 also calculated. The evaluated \mathcal{L}_2 error values confirm good approximations of the numerical solution
 483 with the PINN solution, even for distinctly deformed band profiles of analytes due to the gradient of
 484 the modifier and the competitive adsorption process (Fig. 2D).

485 It should be noted that \mathcal{L}_2 for the second component is larger than for the first one.

486 **Table 3** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A1.

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
B1^{A1}	13.5	0.05	70	1000	0.0343
T1^{A1}	3.1	0.05	40	1000	0.0207 0.0197
B2^{A1}	1	0.16	50	1000	0.0769
T2^{A1}	2	0.20	30	1000	0.0264 0.0786

487

488 It should be noted that in the case of ternary systems the relative \mathcal{L}_2 error was calculated for the first
 489 and second analyte, respectively.

490 **Fig. 2.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED model numerical solutions. Points (A) and (C)
 491 depict a binary system, while (B) and (D) show a ternary system. The first two plots illustrate changes
 492 in inlet concentration ($B1^{A1}$, $T1^{A1}$) and the subsequent two represent variations in injection time ($B2^{A1}$,
 493 $T2^{A1}$).

494

495 **4.5. Model A2: use cases**

496 In **Section 4.4** the simplest process of gradient chromatography separation using the linear gradient of
 497 modifier was analyzed, while in **Section 4.5** other cases have been tested on Model A2.

498 To assess the effectiveness of the Model A2, broadly based setups were trialed in which the
 499 aforementioned parameters were altered. Furthermore, the aspect involving the apparent Peclet number

500 for each component was subjected to gauge the performance as well (see **Section 4.5.3** for further
 501 details). The operating conditions for the specific case studies were summarized in Tables 4-11. It should
 502 be noted here that for experiments depicted in Figs. (5-6) the Peclet number for each component takes
 503 identical value, but differs with the experiments.

504 In addition, we have investigated the impact of noise in the data from the numerical experiments on the
 505 performance of PINN predictions. The corresponding results are presented in **Section 4.5.6**.

506

507 **Table 4** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with different τ_g .

Experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe
B1^{A2}	10	0.05	25	1000
	10	0.05	40	1000
	10	0.05	70	1000
T1^{A2}	4.5	0.025	20	1000
	4.5	0.025	30	1000
	4.5	0.025	50	1000
T2^{A2}	10	0.09	2	2000
	10	0.09	3	2000
	10	0.09	5	2000

508

509

510 **Table 5** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with different α .

Experiment	y_0 [-]	α [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe
T3^{A2}	10	0.70	0.025	40	2000
	10	0.80	0.025	40	2000
	10	0.90	0.025	40	2000

511

512

513 **Table 6** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with different S .

Experiment	γ_0 [-]	S [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe
T4 ^{A2}	10	7	0.025	55	1000
	10	9	0.025	55	1000
	10	13	0.025	55	1000

514

515

516

517

518 **Table 7** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with different Peclet
 519 numbers.

Experiment	γ_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe_a
B2 ^{A2}	10	0.050	60	5
	10	0.050	60	7.5
	10	0.050	60	12.5
T5 ^{A2}	10	0.025	40	20
	10	0.025	40	30
	10	0.025	40	50

520

521

522 **Table 8** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with various apparent
 523 Peclet numbers.

Experiment	γ_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	$Pe_{a,1}$	$Pe_{a,2}$	$Pe_{a,3}$
T6 ^{A2}	10	0.025	40	1000	50	10000
	10	0.025	40	1000	70	10000

10	0.025	40	1000	110	10000
----	-------	----	------	-----	-------

524

525

526

527 **Table 9** Experimental conditions applied to the investigation associated with different $\Delta\phi$
 528 values for step gradient.

Experiment	y_0 [-]	$\Delta\phi$ [V/V]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	$Pe_{a,1}$	$Pe_{a,2}$	$Pe_{a,3}$
T7 ^{A2}	10	0.2	0.025	0.001	1000	50	10000
	10	0.3	0.025	0.001	1000	50	10000
	10	0.4	0.025	0.001	1000	50	10000

529

530

531 **Table 10** Experimental conditions applied to the study associated with altering two variables
 532 simultaneously – values of inlet concentration and time gradient.

Experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe
T8 ^{A2}	2	0.025	25	1000
	2	0.025	30	1000
	4	0.025	30	1000

533

534 **Table 11** Experimental conditions applied to the study associated with altering two variables
 535 simultaneously, i.e. values of injection time and parameter S .

Experiment	y_0 [-]	S [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe
T9 ^{A2}	5	10	0.025	30	1000
	5	10	0.050	30	1000
	5	12	0.050	30	1000

536

537

538 **4.5.1. Gradient duration time, nonlinear gradient.**

539 Here, an evaluation of the dynamics of the chromatographic process involving linear and non-linear
540 gradient elution modes for mixed τ_g , and α , as captured by the PINN, was provided. Training datasets
541 for this section are displayed in Fig. S5-S8 and the corresponding \mathcal{L}_2 errors were summarized in Table
542 12.

543 As before, the PINN solution in the case of τ_g well predicts the numerical one. Interestingly, it is also
544 clearly visible that with decreasing gradient time, the second peak deforms into a rectangular shape
545 (Fig. 3C)

546 However, sometimes it can be difficult to find the appropriate parameters values of the linear gradient
547 of the modifier (Eq. (15)) to obtain a satisfactory result (in our case complete separation of species),
548 especially when several species are expected to be separated. In such cases, the remedy can be a linear
549 piecewise gradient with increasing or decreasing modifier concentration or a gradient following a
550 specific nonlinear function.

551 As an example, assume that the nonlinear change of modifier concentration is described with equation
552 Eq. (35) represented by the green line in Fig. 3D, and α is an adjustable parameter. As can be seen with
553 increasing and subsequently decreasing concentration of modifier the complete separation of the
554 analytes is easily attainable.

555 Although the gradient of the modifier varies significantly in value and direction, the concentration
556 profiles calculated using the PINN coincide with the peak lines calculated using the numerical method.

557

$$558 \quad \varphi(\tau, 0) = \begin{cases} \varphi_0, & 0 \leq \tau < \tau_b \\ \varphi_0 + (\alpha \cdot \tau)^2 \cdot \exp(-\tau), & \tau_b \leq \tau < \tau_b + \tau_g \\ 0, & \tau_b + \tau_g \leq \tau \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

559

560

561 **Table 12** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A2. The case studies in question concern the parameters τ_g –
 562 Eq. (15), and α – Eq. (35).

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe	α	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
B1^{A2}	10	0.05	55	1000	-	0.0314
T1^{A2}	4.5	0.025	40	1000	-	0.0464 0.0604
T2^{A2}	10	0.09	4	2000	-	0.0261 0.0403
T3^{A2}	10	0.025	40	2000	0.85	0.1757 0.0526

563

564

565 **Fig. 3.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED model numerical solutions. Point (A) depicts
 566 binary system, while (B) – (D) shows ternary systems. The (A) – (C) plots illustrate the influence of τ_g
 567 ($B1^{A2}$, $T1^{A2}$, $T2^{A2}$) on chromatography peaks and the chromatogram (D) represents peak variation under
 568 a nonlinear modifier gradient ($T3^{A2}$).

569

570 4.5.2. The effect of modifier on the adsorption process (Eq. (34)).

571 The parameter S is a coefficient used to describe the influence of a modifier on analyte retention. Higher
 572 parameter S indicates a greater contribution of the modifier to the adsorption process, reducing the
 573 analyte's adsorption strength, shortening retention times, and decreasing peak asymmetry.

574 In the following, it was assumed that $S_1 = S_2 = S$. Training datasets for this experiment are displayed
 575 in Fig. S9. Also in this case, the PINN solution correctly predicts the numerical one as presented in
 576 Fig. 4. The corresponding \mathcal{L}_2 errors were summarized in Table 13.

577 **Table 13** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A2. Experimental test conditions for investigation associated with
 578 different S – Eq. (34).

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	S [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
T4 ^{A2}	10	11	0.025	55	1000	0.0325
						0.0394

579

580

581 **Fig. 4.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED model numerical solutions for a case study on
 582 the parameter S (T4^{A2}).

583

584 4.5.3. Performance of prediction elution curves under various Peclet numbers

585 Example 1

586 As already stated, the ED model neglects mass transfer resistances. It takes into account only the
 587 nonideality of the mobile phase flow, which is not plug-type flow. This nonideality is characterized by

588 the dispersion coefficient, D_L , or with the Peclet number in the dimensionless form of the ED model.
589 The larger is Pe number the smaller is dispersion and the narrower is peak of an analyte. If the column
590 works in concentration overload conditions (nonlinear isotherm zone) then with an increase of Pe value
591 above 2000 - 3000 a peak profile remains almost unchanged. So, the PINN method predicts correctly
592 concentration profiles - simulation is not presented.

593

594 In a real chromatographic column, the mass transfer resistance can be so significant that it determines
595 the shape of concentration band profiles. As an example can be a separation of proteins whose effective
596 diameter is of the order of the adsorbent pore diameter. The ED model can also be used in this case,
597 however, the dispersion coefficient D_L has to be replaced by the apparent dispersion coefficient, D_a , or
598 the Peclet number has to be replaced with the apparent Peclet number, Pe_a in the dimensionless model
599 form. The value of D_a or Pe_a can be taken from experiments or calculated from appropriate correlation
600 based on a number of theoretical plates, N [23,49].

601 In practice, the N value can only be a few plates.

602 For such a small value of N , it should be remembered that:

- 603 • the ED model has to be solved with Danckwerts boundary conditions. When $N > 100$ the
604 solution of the ED model with Dirichlet boundary conditions approximates the solution with
605 Danckwerts boundary conditions, the better, the larger is N [46],
- 606 • when $Pe_a/2 < 100$ this tendency is opposite. If Pe_a is used in the ED model then Eq. (22a) from
607 [49] should be used for N calculations.

608

609 Taking the above into account our numerical experiment was restricted to Pe_a values less than about
610 200. Thus, for the binary and the ternary systems, the training datasets shown in Fig. S10 and Fig. S11
611 were employed. The obtained \mathcal{L}_2 errors (Table 14) remain below 0.04, indicating that the numerical
612 experimental performance is in good agreement with the predictions of the neural network. A visual
613 comparison between the exact elution curve and the PINN solution for both systems is presented in Fig.
614 5.

615

616 **Table 14** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A2. Experimental test conditions for investigation associated with
 617 different Peclet numbers.

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe_a	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
B2 ^{A2}	10	0.050	60	10	0.0279
					0.0366
T5 ^{A2}	10	0.025	40	40	0.0347

618

619 **Fig. 5.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED numerical model solutions. Points (A) and (B)
 620 depict binary (B2^{A2}) and ternary systems (T5^{A2}), respectively, for a case study of various Pe_a .

621

622 **Example 2**

623 In this example, different values of $Pe_{a,i}$ for analytes, and modifiers were assumed. Indices $i = 1$,
 624 and $i = 2$ refer to analytes, and index $i = 3$ to modifiers, respectively.

625 In practice, substances of small molecules are used as modifiers, such as methanol, acetonitrile, and
 626 similar. The mass transfer resistances are very small and $Pe_{a,3} = 10000$ can be assumed.

627 On the other hand, let's assume that the second analyte consists of large molecules with a diameter
 628 similar to pore diameter size. In such a case, the mass transfer resistances would be large, and the Peclet
 629 number is very low. As a result, $Pe_{a,2} < 200$ can be assumed. Finally, assuming that the first analyte is
 630 not very large or very small $Pe_{a,1} = 1000$ can be accepted.

631 The training datasets illustrated in Fig. S12 were utilized, and the evaluated \mathcal{L}_2 errors were presented
 632 in Table 15. It can be seen in Fig. 6 that the predicted concentration profiles align well with the reference
 633 elution curves of the analytes, which is also corroborated by the obtained errors being below 0.04.

634

635 **Table 15** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A2. Experimental test conditions for investigations associated with
 636 various apparent Peclet numbers.

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	$Pe_{a,1}$	$Pe_{a,2}$	$Pe_{a,3}$	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
T6 ^{A2}	10	0.025	40	1000	90	10000	0.0346
							0.0405

637

638

639

640 **Fig. 6.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED model numerical solutions for a case study of
 641 various $Pe_{a,2}$ ($T6^{A2}$).

642

643 4.5.4. Performance of prediction elution curves under various $\Delta\varphi$

644 The last example of exploring gradient shapes is devoted to the step gradient. The step gradient is applied
 645 when the separation of analytes is poor. This shape of the gradient was approximated including very
 646 low value of τ_g in linear gradient formulae Eq. (15), i.e. $\tau_g = 0.001[-]$. A distinct step growth of the
 647 modifier concentration can facilitate the separation of components.

648 The training datasets shown in Fig. S13 were employed. The apparent Pe_a values are given in Table 14
 649 9. The obtained \mathcal{L}_2 errors (Table 14 16) are the largest among the investigated examples. However, the
 650 analyzed problem was the most difficult to solve due to very steep concentration changes. By using the
 651 trained PINN model, a significant reduction in computational time was obtained since the PINN
 652 computational time was almost 272 times shorter compared to the OCFE method.

653 A visual comparison between the exact elution curve and the PINN is presented in Fig. 7.

654

655

656 **Table 16** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A2. Experimental test conditions below for investigation are
 657 associated with different $\Delta\phi$.

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	$\Delta\phi$	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	$Pe_{a,1}$	$Pe_{a,2}$	$Pe_{a,3}$	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
T7 ^{A2}	10	0.35	0.025	0.001	1000	50	10000	0.0818
								0.1538

658

659

660 **Fig. 7.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED model numerical solutions for a case study of
 661 various $\Delta\phi$ (T7^{A2}).

662

663 **4.5.5. Performance in predicting elution curves with different values of two operational**
 664 **parameters**

665 The possibility of making predictions for several different parameters enhances the application area of
 666 the PINN model, therefore this section covers results for simultaneous variation of the parameters ω
 667 and ξ .

668 The following cases were considered with various process configurations: firstly, a modification in inlet
 669 concentration accompanied by a change in time gradient; and secondly, an alteration to the S parameter
 670 coupled with a simultaneous modification in injection time. The detailed operating conditions for
 671 training the neural network are shown in Tables 10-11, while the datasets are visualized in Figs. S14-
 672 S15.

673 The \mathcal{L}_2 error results indicate that the PINN model delivers better performance when both the y_0 and τ_g
 674 parameters (**T8^{A2}**) are modified simultaneously. However, it should be noted that a visual assessment of
 675 the predicted concentration profiles for **T9^{A2}** suggests that the outcomes remain acceptable, despite the
 676 higher \mathcal{L}_2 error.

677 **Table 17** The \mathcal{L}_2 errors for model A2. Experimental test conditions for investigation associated with
 678 altering two variables simultaneously.

Test experiment	y_0 [-]	S [-]	τ_p [-]	τ_g [-]	Pe	Relative \mathcal{L}_2 error
T8^{A2}	3	—	0.025	25	1000	0.0354
						0.0864
T9^{A2}	5	11	0.025	30	1000	0.1799
						0.1411

679

680

681 **Fig. 8.** Comparison of the PINN predicted and the ED model numerical solutions for a case study, where
 682 (A) inlet concentration and τ_g were varied (T8^{A2}), (B) injection time and parameter S were varied
 683 (T9^{A2}).

684

685 4.5.6. The effect of noise on PINN predictive performance

686 It is acknowledged that real experiment data are subject to noise, which occurs at the detector acquisition
 687 stage and can be also attributed to the pump and autosampler instabilities, fluid flow velocity
 688 disturbances and other factors. In the preceding sections, the results presented were based on *in silico*
 689 generated data. Therefore, in order to reflect the experimental conditions, a trial was conducted to assess
 690 the robustness of a PINN when exposed to noise in the provided data. For this purpose, a 5% random
 691 noise was introduced into the dataset displayed in Fig. S5 (see Supplementary material for further details
 692 & Table 4 B1^{A2}), thereby **emulating** real chromatographic conditions (Fig. 9).

693

694

695 **Fig. 9.** Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for PINN training under different τ_g , where 5%
 696 of noise is present.

697

698 As expected, the application of PINN model effectively reduces the introduced noise, thus providing
 699 predictive accuracy comparable to that achieved using the strict numerical data used in previous studies.

700 The predicted concentration profile obtained for the test case, i.e. $\tau_g = 55$ by PINN trained model is
 701 presented in Fig. 10.

702

703 **Fig. 10.** Comparison of the PINN model solution, trained in the presence of 5% noisy data with the
 704 numerical solution of the ED model.

705

706 Unsurprisingly, the PINN model was able to compensate the noise present in provided data with relative
 707 \mathcal{L}_2 error of 0.0737, due to the fact that physics-informed machine learning can seamlessly integrate both
 708 the data and the governing physical laws. This effectiveness could be especially beneficial for practical,
 709 real-world applications. Moreover, the example demonstrates the true potential of PINN in uncovering
 710 GLC dynamics, where adsorption isotherm is implicit.

711

712 **5. Conclusions**

713 This is the first attempt, to the best of our believe when the PINN approach was applied to gradient
 714 liquid chromatography to predict concentration profiles under various elution conditions, such as linear
 715 and nonlinear gradient elution mode, slow and fast gradient adjustment as well as step-type GLC, and
 716 gradient coupled with mass transfer resistances. To address our concept, two distinct PINN models,
 717 termed as A1 and A2 have been proposed. Information pertaining to the complex dynamics of species

718 separation was embedded into a loss function and captured by the neural network throughout the
719 training phase. Primarily, the learning process entailed matching the provided labeled data and
720 minimizing PDE residuals. Additionally, the adsorption isotherm, Q , was implicit to the PINNs, forcing
721 the models to estimate this parameter from the available data. Furthermore, Dirichlet or Danckwerts
722 boundary conditions were enforced in the developed PINNs.

723 The selection of appropriate weights, λ , specifying the contribution of the individual terms of the loss
724 function is challenging and affects significantly predictive capabilities. Herein, these parameters were
725 found through trial and error approach.

726 Comprehensive numerical experiments, including the variability of multiple parameters were carried
727 out as comparative tests of the obtained predictions. The performance highlights the high predictive
728 capability of the proposed models.

729 Determining the optimal conditions for chromatographic separation relies on carefully selected and
730 performed experiments followed by analytical or numerical solving of classical mathematical column
731 models (e.g. GR, ED, etc.) and can be a tedious task often requiring even thousands of model solutions.
732 Furthermore, the calculation time for process optimization based on numerical methods can be very
733 long. In this paper, we have demonstrated that a trained PINN model allows for a significant reduction
734 in computation time, since it proved to be 272 times faster comparing to the OCFE method.

735 Nevertheless, further research into the use of the Physics-Informed Neural Networks is needed. Our
736 future work will focus on exploring the applications of the PINNs, particularly with regard to GLC.

737

738 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

739 All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

740

741 **Supplementary materials**

742 Additional information is provided in the file Supplementary material.docx.

743

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748

749 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

750 **Filip Rękas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal

751 analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – original draft preparation, Writing –

752 review and editing, Visualization

753 **Marcin Chutkowski:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing –

754 original draft preparation, Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Project administration

755 **Krzysztof Kaczmarek:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Data Curation,

756 Writing – original draft preparation, Writing – review and editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition

757

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